

SOCIO –ECONOMIC CONDITION OF DONGRIA KANDHA IN ODISHA

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INRODUCTION

The kandha tribe is variously known .they are called the khand or the kondh or the kondh, according to the usage of the term in vogue in different places in which they live. But whatever be the terminology used, it refers to the same tribe the people of that class call themselves the kondh as a result of their contact with heoriya so we refer to them as the kondhin this paper this nomenclature is believed to have come from the telugu language in which the word kandha means a small hillas well as the hill –men. Kalahandi, is a district of orissa in India. Kalahandi, the picturesque landmark of Orissa became a district after merger of princely states. It is bounded by Kandhamal districts, Rayagada districts, on the east and Nawarangpur districts of Orissa and Chhattisgarh province on the west .On the north of this district situated Nuapada and Balangir districts and on the south bounded by Nawarangpur district. Kalahandi districts is predominated by tribals. tribals like Banjara , Bhatra , Bhunjia , Binjhal , Dal , Gond , Kandha , Mirdha , Munda , Paraja , Saora and Savaretc ... The main sub – tribes kutiakandha ,desiakandha , Dongariakandha are inhabiting in kalahandi district . mainly kandhas are concentrated in Bhawanipatna , Junagarh , Narla, Koksara , Kalampur , Lanjigarh , jayapatna , Madanpur – rampur , Thuamul –rampur blocks . Kandhas claim as the first settlers in the district they were the owners of all the lands of the districts in the past . so the land was named as kandhan or kandhan des . Among the kandhas of kalahandi many sub – groups are found. According to dr. krishansharmadangaria ,kuvi , kuttia , languli, penga and jharania sub – groups of kandha are found in the district . Other scholars opined regarding their division as per following –

1. Desia or kachhariakandha ,kutia / kotiakandha/ dangriakandha .
2. Dongaria ,kuvi , kutia , languli , penga, and jharania .
3. Dangria, jangalia ,nanglya , pataria , des kandha , jharania and maral .
4. Kutia ,dangaria , jharania , desia , desakandha, dal kandha and maral .

Dal kandha, kandhaparaja ,maral , suliakandhaetc ..sub– groups of kandhas are also found in this area.

Different researcher provide the different divisions of the kandhas

→ According to dr. krishna sharma kandhas are divide in to seven , that are I) Sika II) Luha III) Uccharia IV) Tupa V) BadhudkaVI) Gaanka VII) Budka

→ According to dr. Dol Govinda Bisi kandhas are divided into Dal, Sika, Kurmilkya , Turkyia , Balaringya , Kudurkyia , Charmilikya, Beska, Uchrya , Ghusurya , Kanbiria , Kungibadka , Lua , Dhumnia , Tupa , Bubrya , Chimkyia , desghriya .

→ Different locality kandhas are known as different names such as –

- Kesinga kandhas are known as chaks
- Sainatala kandhas are known as Sika
- Th . Rampur kandhas are known as Tuduka and bijulka and sermelka .

They speak “KUI” and “KUVI” language . kandhas are mostly found in koraput , kalahandi , bolangir ,phulbani districts of odisha . In kalahandi the kandhas are mostly found in lanjigarh , Madanpur –Rampur , Thuamul- Rampur , Bhawanipatna , Narla , Junagarh ,Koksara, Kalampur, Kesinga blocks. kandhas are honest and minimalist people they are down to the earth their worship like jani , majhi , mallick , konhar are some common surnames of kandha people . Kandhas like – I) Kutia kandha II) Dongria kandha III) Desia kandha

Are mainly found in odisha other than sitha kandha , pengo kandha , malua kandha , buda kandha are also found in odisha there are 62 tribal groups are found but kandha tribes are found in mejurity kandhas were well known for their maria sacrifice or Human sacrifice called brutal acts .

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The education status of the dongria kandhas is not so good . 90% of dongria kandhas were illiterate and 10% are literate between that female litereracy rate is 3% and male literacy rate is 7%. The dongria kandhas are included in primitive tribal groups (PTG) . in odisha mostly dongria kandhas were found and they stay on mountains they depend upon natures and they involve in primary activities . In odisha they are found in niyamgiri hill regions and further they spread in to kalahandi district , Rayagada district and Koraput district of odisha . Dongria kandhas are found in muniguda , kalyansinghpur and Bissamcuttack region of the Rayagada districts . more than 10,000 dongria kandha tribe are found in kalayansinghpur , Bissamcuttack and Muniguda regions of Rayagada districts . The dongria kandha were speak kui language also known as kuvi language . they extended over more than 120 villages and according to data their sex ratio is 1352 female per 1000 males .

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF KANDHA TRIBE

Kandha word is come from the telgu that is konda, the meaning of konda is hill , because kandhas are hill dwellers . they also known as Tanla gouda . There are desia kandha . kutia kandhas , dongria kandhas and other several division of kandha tribes are found in odisha . The dongria kandhas were found in the hilly regions and they mostly depends on natures and horticulture where as desia and kutia kandhas were depend upon agriculture for their livelihood . they are earthy people .Mr. russell provided the 1st report about the kandha communities . Another person who work for kandhas is Swami lakshmanananda saraswati in august 2008 . In india kandhamal district is a part of red corridor . there are several conflicts were happen during the enquire for their development . The society is made up large families group known as totem .the leader of kandhas society called kandha pradhan . the leader is the most powerful person in the society . Kandhas or kondhas or khonds are all same word . khonds are originally Adivasi tribal group of india . they depend up on the agricultural processes and practice hunting and gathering .

According to 2011 census their population is more than 1, 627,486 of kandhas and khonds tribal groupes people speak kui and kuvi language . KUI and KUVI is their native language . and write odia .Kandhas were praclised worship of shamanism and nature and also worship of human sacrifices. There are several rituals of khonds are – i. Jhagadi ii . Meriah puja iii. Dharni penu puja iv. Sru penu puja v . Pitabali puja vi. Guraba penu puja vii. Turki penu puja

viii. kedu puja human sacrifices is the worship of meriah puja , dharni puja is for earth , saru penu puja is the sacrifices of fowls ,Dehuri puja is the sacrifices of goat and chicken , Turki penu puja and gurba penu puja is done out side of the village and the last and important Pitabali puja where the sacrifices of buffalo . **LOCATION OF THE KANDHA**

The kandhas are found in the four district of the odisha that is Kandhamal , Koraput , Kalahandi and Rayagada district of odisha . the region like Lanjigarh in Kalahandi , Bisamcuttack , Munigada in Rayagada etc are the region of kandhas the kalahandi district is 19°3 North and 21°5 latitude and 83° 47 East longitude . The district likr Nuapada , Koraput , Rayagada , Nabarangpur , Balangir , Boudh , Kandhamal are the neighbour district of Kalahandi . According to census 2001 the population of kalahandi is 13,35,494 . the total area is 7, 920 km² , according to area the kalahandi district is n 7th number in the odisha state . the most of the part of kalahandi is surrounded by the mountains , hilly region like lanjigarh etc the area is found as dense forest cover region.

POPULATION OF DONGRIA KANDHA TRIBE

The dongria kandha tribes population according to census 1991 is 1,46 , 225 in kalahandi district the other division of kandhas are kutia kandha tribes , desia kandha tribes and dongaria kandha tribe they are spread over the kalahandi district , koraput district , rayagada district and kandhamal district . In kalahandi kandhas are found in Lanjigarh , m.rampur , th.rampur , junagarh , koksara , kalampur and some part of jaypatna hilly regions . The dongria kandhas tribes group are found

in the hilly regions of kalahandi , odisha . in kalahandi district dongria kandha were mostly found in lanjigarh block . they found in lanjigarh niyamgiri hill regions .

They also found in other district like koraput district , kandhamal and rayagada district region like bissamcutack , muniguda etc .They are spread over the odisha hilly regions for their livelihood . more than 8,000 population is found on the lanjigarh niyamgiri hills . they prefer primary activities , they practise crop cultivation and mostly depend up on the hills for natural resources . they also practise shifting cultivation method for their livelihood . they mostly eat the hilly regions fruits like mango , jackfruit etc .. due to lack of food availability they mostly involve in under weight problems and malnutrition like health problems . The traditional dance of kandhas are kutia kandhas dance that they enjoy on their festival . the kutia kandha dance is famous but other dances also found that are stick dance , singa dances were perform by the kandhas

Population of dongria kandha

A baseline survey by scheduled castes and scheduled tribes research and training institute (2016)odisha reveals that the total dongriakandha population in kalahandi district 7,722 (4,443 women and 3,279men) living in 1,892 family . they live in 98 villages with extremely minimal infrastructure facilities for instance , only of these villages have school , while 28 villages have anganwadicentres . only 16 villages are connected with motorable road . the literacy rate among the dongriakandha is % out of which the male literacy rate is 24.5% and the female literacy rate is 15.9% according to the survey .

TABLE NO -2 POPULATION OF DONGRIA KANDHA

Demography , literacy and available basic infrastructure for dongria kandha in niyamgiri –

Source – Scs & STs research institute (SCSTRTI),government of odisha (2016).

Language

The dongria kandha belong to the dravidian linguistic group . G. A. Grierson has written , “the kandhas or khonds are dravidian tribe in the hills of orissa and neighbouring districts. the name which they use themselves is kui and their language should accordingly be dominated kui” .

Kui is not written , but it is spoken among the people of kandha community but now odia language also speak of kandha community.

Sattlement Pattern

The villages of the dongria kandha are located in a tangle of thickly wooded hill ranges . the earliest ones are situated in the valleys and the later ones either in the hill slopes or at the hill top . the suitability of a site for habitation is determined by the availability of sufficient land for shifting cultivation and a perennial source of watersupply . Apart of the availability of the resources , every construction of a house in a new site is preceded by a magico- religious divination to ascertain ritual worthiness or otherwise of the site. Both the person concerned and the medicine –man go to the site before dusk after taking bath . the former digs a pit at the middle of the site . then the latter puts some unboiled white rice in the pit ,covers the grains with a leaf cup made of siali –leaves and at the end of the rite sprinkles water over the cup by reciting some magical formula . there after both of them leave the place and proceed non-stop homeward without looking backward . next day both of them come to the spot to see what has happened to the grains . if the grains are scattered then they conclude that the ancestors of the person concerned do not want him to stay there and otherhand if they find that the grains are intact then it is concluded that the ancestors have indicated that the site is auspicious and therefore, approve of the site for building the proposed house .

The houses are built closed to each other conforming to a linear pattern . a narrow street runs from one end to the other of the village separating the two rows of houses.

At the entry of the village , which is marked by mango grove and jack –fruit trees , a shed thatched with bamboo splits is built to represent the shrine of the village deity called jatrakudi penu who is believed to protect the people from evil –eye . a straw-thatched shed called kuddi is built in the middle of the village street to lodge the earth – goddess .

They have no habit of wearing any foot-wears . men are skilled in making hats out of siali leaves. They use to wash and clean their clothes and kosla- rice powder to stiffen the clothes . now – a-days , use of soap is common in almost all households. Ordinary clothes are kept on a baboo pole hanged against wall of the sleeping room . one or tow pairs of washed clothes are kept in the bamboo basket which used on ceremonial occasions .

A women uses two peces of cloth each ,three feet in length and one –and half in width . the first piece is wrapped round the waist with a knot in the front .the second piece hangs around the waist and one end of it passes through the arm-pits and tied at the back to cover the upper part of the body a small piece of cloth is always used by an adult women as an underwear . but now they prefer to wear one piece saree which is available in the local market.

Both men and women use a wrapper over their body in winter . women of economically better off family wear saree with red boarders . but now a days different colour and cotton saree also wear .

Traditionally dongria kandha women are very fond of making different tattoo (tikanguhpa) designs on the face .

on ceremonial occasion , clean cloths or new clothes are used . men prefer to wear shirts & joti and women wear saree and both men and women decorated their body with ornaments .

Ornaments

The dongria kandha , both males and females including children are very much fond of ornaments with which they adorn themselves ordinarily and look attractive . the dongria males grow long hair as proverbially required by the mythicak niyam raja to differentiate themselves from other sections of the kandha and prepare braided locks like the females at their sculps . they cannot afford to put on golden ornaments , but usually ornaments made out of silver , brass ,and alloys are used .A wooden comb is fixed at the hair knot irrespective of sex which adorns the hair –lock and keeps the hair tight . a tiny knife with two colourfullthread balls at its bell – metal handle ,is used by the ladies .

Food

Generally the dongria kandha eat three times a day – once in the morning at about 8.00 am , once in midday at about 1.00 pm and once in the night at about 7.00 pm as the people go out early morning to work in their dongar field they carry along with them the morming and midday meals to the field . when they come back from field in the evening they take the night meal at home . the morning meal consists of only ragi – gruel and a pinch of salt . the same food is taken at midday with cooked green leaves . and the night meal either ragi gruel cooked with rice or unboiled rice and with vegetable curry . they are fond of fish . they take it after baking directly on fire . liquor is locally called kalu . various kinds of liquor are brewed domestically suh as , mahua liquor , mango – liquor , jackfruit – liquor , banana liquor , molasses – liquor , and sago –palm juice , an intoxicated drink is collected from locally available sago- palm trees . Parents and children sit down together for taking their food . the wife serves food to her husband and children first and after then she takes her food .this is the manner of taking food while in the field . but at home the older members are served food first and next the head of the household and children . and women take their food at last . and then they finish eating , they sweep the floor and clean the place where they food eating . It is the duty of women to cook food and childern above 7 to 8 years of age , help their mothers in cooking . normally men do not cook but when women are menstrual period the burden of cooking falls on men .

Collection of firewood is the work of both men and women . it is stored in the back varendah of the house and used for cooking food .

Sources of livelihood

The important sources of livelihood of the dongria kandha –

i) agriculture and horticulture

ii) forest collection

iii) trade

iv) animal husbandry

Agriculture –

The entire tract of the niyamgiri hill ranges is situated on the eastern ghats. In view of the altitude , soil and climatic condition , the people are forced to practise sifting cultivation as there is no plain land for wet – cultivation . all the socio- cultural and socio – economic practices therefore , veer round the shifting cultivation of the dongria kandha .

The land in the dongria region is divided in to three categories –

i) hill slopes or top of hill – haru

ii) land at the foot of hills – penga

iii) lands adjoining the hamlets – bada

Shifting cultivation –

Dongria kandha traditionally dwells in hilly and forest area , due to the absence of permanent plains land they adopt shifting cultivation to sustain . they consider forest is their asset and clears the patch of forest land for shifting cultivation depends upon the strength and stamina of family . all the cleared bushes and twigs were burnt and wait for the rain before sowing . once the monsoon is active they sow all variety of seeds includes pulses , millets , paddy , vegetables, grains by making small furrows with digging stick .

The technology used for this type of cultivation is very simple requires only some digging sticks , hand axe , sickle , crowbar and spade . the crops grow naturally and the burnt ashes act as good manure for the growth of crops in the cleared land . they do not use animals, pesticides and inorganic manure in shifting cultivation process . after harvest they leave the cultivated land fallow , abandon it and move to next fresh patch of land for another cycle of shifting cultivation .

SOCIAL ORGANISATION

Family : The family is the smallest social group consisting in the simplest form of parents and unmarried children . such nuclear type of family is the most common among the Dongria Kandha . when a son is grown up and gets married he sets up his own house and lives there with his wife and children . some times if space permits a new room is added to the old house and the married son is accommodated in it . 90 % family are nuclear only 10 % are joint family in Dongria villages. The family is not only a social unit but also an economic unit . all the able bodied adult members and even the children above 5 year of age toil in the field and contribute to the common economic pool of the family . Men do ploughing and cutting trees and women do cleaning and fields , particularly in the hill slopes and make them fit for growing crops .

The men make holes in the fields and the women who follow them dibble seeds into them. Life in Dongria Kandha family is most peaceful and without conflict and tension , husband and wife are partners in all walks of life . the husband never shows any disrespect to his wife and seeks her advice in all social and economic matters . both of them work together at home and in the field , one helping the other in such ways as the custom of their society dictates.

Among the Dongria Kandha The older people are highly respected by the younger people .

SOCIAL CONTROL

Leadership

Leadership pattern of the Dongria Kandhas through light on their socio political organization . in Kandhas society the position of the leaders in a society is very important. A leader not only

enjoy status and high prestige in the society , but they also exercise considerable authority in getting things done in the most correct manner. The leaders may be classified as traditional and modern depending on their offices , or their roles . the community at large is composed of such families and since this is more or less based on kinship , each family acts in conformity with accepted mode

A leaders shoulder all responsibilities , participate in all social activities and effectively influence the life of their fellowmen . the traditional leader are focus on hereditary status and position . they arrangement of the society . they are oriented towards development of their society activities .they are progressive and government agencies and the people .

GOVERNMENT SCHEME FOR DEVELOPMENT OF KANDHA

The DRDA (District Rural Development Agency) and ITDAS (Integratred Tribal Development Agencies) were practise various social and economic deveelopment programmes for the kandhas people the phulbani and balliguda blocks of kandhamal district work for development of kandha tribes . The government establish the agency for the development of dongria kandha in rayagada district of chatikona village . The odisha government establish the programme OPELIP for the development of dongria kandha . OPELIP means (Odisha PVTG Empowerment and Livelihoods Improvement Programme) . this OPELIP is started from the 2016 and this OPELIP programe was implemented in 12 District and 89 Gram or Village of odisha . the aim of OPELIP is to reduce the poverty level of the dongria kandha , development in their health sector , development in their education system , and improve their life style etc . The Government of odisha created the development agency for the dongria kandha tribes . the ST SC DD agency was establish by the odisha government for the improvement and development of schedule tribes and schedules castes . they work for planning related work for kandhas , providing funds they also created the committee for programme management . the programme management committee provide support from FNGOS .they work for empowerment , management of natural resources , enchancing their livelihood .

CONCLUSION -

However it is glade to involve on this research regarding kandha , where I have been study or persona;;y research on different type of kandha . accure many experience and their lifestyle and activites . I have collected lots of experience on kandha tribe of different place and type . as we know kandha is one of the most popular tribe in kalahandi or odisha . and it is believed that they are the earlier residents of this native place . When I started my research on kandha tribe in remote region of kalahandi I was very fear because they are living in deep forest but it was my myth . when I meet with them they were instantly familiar with me .In this period of my research I studied their social , political , economical , cultural , educational and government schemes both states and central for theme and other activities . which has described briefly in my research . I got enormous experience which give me satisfaction .

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